

EVALUATION OF RSSI-BASED HUMAN TRACKING

Juha Latvala, Jari Syrjärinne*, Hannu Ikonen, and Jarkko Niittylahti

Digital and Computer Systems, Tampere University of Technology,
P.O.Box: 553, Tampere, FINLAND

*Nokia Mobile Phones, Research & Technology
P.O.Box 429, FIN-33101 Tampere, FINLAND
e-mail: juha.latvala@tut.fi

ABSTRACT

This paper evaluates a location and tracking system built on an existing wireless local area network (WLAN). The tracking system is implemented without any additional hardware and is implementable in any WLAN environment with minor verification of basestation positioning. The tracking system utilizes the easily extractable signal strength values of the WLAN in order to calculate a position estimate for the observed target. This tracking system is designed to work within predefined surroundings, such as offices, hospitals, prisons etc., with an accuracy of one room.

1. POSITIONING AND TRACKING IN A PREDEFINED ENVIRONMENT

Even though no system has been designed to track and locate targets in a wireless network, extensive study has been given to the similar tracking problem in cellular phone networks. Excluding the GPS solutions, most of them use either different variations of ‘angle of arrival’ (AOA) solutions, or solution models observing ‘time of arrival’ (TOA), ‘observed time differences’ (OTD) or ‘time difference of arrival’ (TDOA)[5][7]. These solution models require highly accurate clock synchronization, and would require additional hardware if they were to be implemented in an indoors tracking system. This is because there is no way of determining the original arrival bearing of the signal, nor is there a possibility to accurately measure time differences of arrived signals using standard stations in WLAN. In the solution presented here, the main emphasis in the tracking system was given on its low-effort implementation and the possibility to add tracking capabilities to an existing WLAN environment. Thus, location estimation is done purely by using the received signal strength indicator (RSSI) values obtained from the communication between the mobile stations (MS) and the base stations (BS).

Fig. 1. Triangulation of MS location with RSSI-values.

In a wireless network, the mobile stations have to be aware of other stations. In order to accomplish this, they constantly keep log of signal power levels of the base stations located in close proximity. Usually, there are several other values that indicate other aspects of link quality, such as actual packets received and overall throughput. However, these are omitted as uninteresting for this particular application. The link quality to BS must be monitored in order to accomplish roaming, a feature enabling seamless transfer of the MS's access point into a larger wired network [1][2]. These signal power levels, or received signal strength indicators, give an estimate of the distance between a particular BS and MS. When at least three values between BSs and an MS are available, it is possible to triangulate the location of the MS. It is possible to use either A. the RSSI values received from BSs to MS or B. vice versa. If choice B. is to be used, the signal strengths must be controlled artificially, as normally the MS will adjust its signal strength to avoid overhearing and ‘near-far’ problems.

Gosh and Lore suggest that a Power Up Function (PUF) could be used to briefly highlight the MS, thus increasing its visibility, and thereby allowing greater distances between BSs [9]. Gosh and Lore indicate that when using this kind of infrastructural approach in locating the MS, usage of PUF gives a clear advantage. On the other hand, some interference is experienced.

The more straightforward method A. is chosen for examination in this application in order to keep the electromagnetic interference within standards. In order to be able to calculate position estimates for the mobile units, fixed locations must be known for the BSs. The relation between the MS's location estimate and the range estimate between MS and BS is given as

$$\hat{r}_i(k|k-1) = \sqrt{[\hat{x}(k|k-1) - x_i]^2 + [\hat{y}(k|k-1) - y_i]^2} \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{r}_i(k|k-1)$ is the estimated range from the i th BS at k , $\hat{x}(k)$, $\hat{y}(k)$ is the estimated position of the MB at k , and x_i, y_i is the fixed position of the i th BS. Fig. 1 demonstrates the basic idea of target triangulation using RSSI values. Here a distance estimate has been counted for each BS. The most probable position for the target is at the intersection of the distance circles.

2. USAGE OF RSSI VALUES

Unfortunately, the RSSI values in a WLAN convert rather poorly into cartesian coordinates. This is mainly due to the serious dampenings and reflections that occur in an office environment due to the high frequency bandwidths used in WLAN. A relevant criteria for the successful usage of RSSI values is the material of the building and, especially in modern office buildings, the amount of steel grid usage in adjacent walls. This means that in every new environment some calibration must be made, so that the conversion of RSSI values would be as accurate as possible. We suggest that at least three different types of BS surrounding type modifiers should be introduced in order to indicate whether the BS is in a virtual Faraday's box, inside heavy walls, or in the open. With these modifiers, it is possible to roughly calibrate the tracking environment when it is initially implemented.

Furthermore, RSSI values are not the best possible indicator for the closeness of the target since they are heavily averaged values and slow in responding to changes. There are instants of time when no values can be read from the nearby stations. These non-ideal features of RSSI-values make direct triangulation poor at best. To deal with these unidealistic features, an extended Kalman filter is applied.

3. EXTENDED KALMAN-FILTER

To improve the reliability of the system and to cope with the occasional lack of measurement data, a Kalman filter was added to the system. Kalman filter provides an efficient and versatile algorithm to the recursive tracking problem. It is also capable of maintaining an acceptable state estimate even if no measurements are available or if they

are at times highly distorted. However, the ideal form of the filter assumes that the state-vector and the measurement vector have a linear relationship. As Equation (1) shows, this is not the case in this application. Therefore, an linearized form of the filter, an extended Kalman filter (EKF) is used. The linearization is accomplished using Taylor series expansion [3][4].

When tracking human targets, the state vector in EKF is assumed to contain position and speed estimates as follows.

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} x^T & \dot{x}^T \end{bmatrix}^T = \begin{bmatrix} x & y & \dot{x} & \dot{y} \end{bmatrix}^T, \quad (2)$$

where x^T is the position of the target in cartesian coordinates, and accordingly, $\dot{x}^T$ the velocity of the target. This assumes motion in straight lines, which was deemed sufficient enough. Since acceleration in human movement is virtually of no consequence, it is neglected. As a matter of fact, in certain cases it is feasible to drop even the speed from the state vector, thus reducing it to location only estimation. In Fig. 5, the difference between location-only and speed-and-location estimation results are presented. The initial estimation point was set purposely on an erroneous position to be able to monitor how quickly and correctly the values would converge to the correct position. The results indicate that when monitoring human movement in a defined environment using erratic measurements, position-only estimation gives more stable results, while accordingly being much slower in reacting to position changes. As a typical human is stationary most of the time, and when moving, does it slowly from the sensors viewpoint, the method serves its purpose.

The measurement data can be processed parallelly or sequentially. Usually, if there is a possibility to use parallel processing it gives better results, as one false measurement has less impact on the location estimate than in sequential processing. Due to the origin of RSSI-values, sequential

Fig. 2. Floor layout of test environment

processing is the only sensible option in this application. The time it takes to extract an RSSI-value depends greatly on how well the MS hears its master-station. Furthermore, the stations within the range of the MS are pinged sequentially. Therefore, parallel processing would at any given time instant use measurement values extracted at different time moments. These itself would introduce error to the location estimate.

4. TESTS CONDUCTED IN AN OFFICE ENVIRONMENT

The tracking system was tested in two different office environments using four BS and one MS. The tracking system was calibrated by taking stationary data from several points across the office floor, and adapting the RSSI conversion function accordingly. Fig. 2 shows the floor layout of the test environment. Stars mark the places of BS's used in tests. When considering the placement of BS's it is important to make sure that all enterable locations have at least three BS to use as reference stations. Otherwise, all range estimates might intersect at several points, causing an ambiguous situation where the location estimate is defined only in one axis. As can be see in Fig. 2 tracking does require some thought on the placement of the BS:s, but the overall increase in the amount of BS:s is insignificant.

Fig. 3. x-coordinate deviation (above) y-coordinate deviation (below).

Fig. 5. Differences between position- (above) and position-speed estimates (below)

The state estimate fluxuates usually within 2 meters of the correct position for stationary targets, and 4 meters for moving. Fig. 4 shows location estimate versus the correct position for a stationary target. Both x and y axes are shown in the same figure. The parameters in EKF must reflect the rapidly changing RSSI-values to maintain an acceptable location estimate. Fig. 3 shows the deviation of location estimates from the EKF in meters for both x and y coordinates. During this test run the root mean square (RMS) accuracy was observed to be about 3 meters The test was performed on a target moving with a constant speed of 0.3 m/s through an L-shaped test track with several stops.

Fig. 4. Position fluxuation for stationary data

5. CONCLUSIONS

The RSSI-based human tracking with extended Kalman filtering proposes a new possibility for indoor human tracking. The implementation is done purely by software, thus requiring no additional devices. The only requirement is a functional WLAN and in certain cases small adjustment of the BS:s location. The tracking system requires that omnidirectional antennas are used in all BS:s.

It is clear that tracking within a rooms accuracy can easily be achieved with RSSI-based tracking, even in a noisy environment and occasional zero-measurements. Extended accuracy can be achieved by introducing map-overlay and constraints to EKF. In the future work will emphasize on making the tracking system more robust, and enhancing the accuracy even further. Work will also concentrate on making the calibration of a new environment easier. Most problems in RSSI-based tracking arise from the non-linear changes in RSSI-values with respect to distance from BS.

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